

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LONG DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	01	25	King George Island	S	62 15	W 58	48
End	2022	02	23	Punta Arenas	S	53 15	W 70	54

CAMPAIGN OBJECTIVE

The main objective of the Tara Antarctic leg was two-fold:

- (i) to sample across well-established physical and biogeochemical gradients
- (ii) to conduct a multi-day process study around an iceberg

Both are concerned with capturing the response of the microbiome to variability in the seascape introduced by topography, frontal systems and freshwater (both melting sea ice, glaciers and icebergs). These scientific objectives are motivated by the urgent need to understand how the microbiome of the Antarctic seas will respond to climate change, as well as to generate baseline understanding in this under-sampled region.

PARTICIPANTS

	ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Martin Hertau
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Nico Bin
3	CREW – Chief Engineer	Loic Caudan
4	CREW -	Mathieu Oriot
5	CREW -	Francois Aurat
6	CREW - Cook	Carole Pire
7	CREW - Media	Maeva Bardy
8	GUEST	Vincent Jolly
9	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Thomas Linkowsky
10	SCIENCE - B – W-Lab biogeochem.	Léa Olivier
11	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Douglas Couet
12	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochem.	Nastassia Patin
13	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Chris Bowler
14	SCIENCE – F – Chief Scientist	Alessandro Tagliabue

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

At the start of the voyage we had to wait 5 days for a replacement oceanographic engineer to arrive due to COVID complications. During this time we sailed to Deception Island and conducted a soak of the Geotraces rosette in the Bransfield strait. Following the arrival of the replacement, we navigated directly into Antarctic Sound to conduct a test station leeward of Dundee Island.

In general, although the prevailing sea ice conditions were very favourable for the navigation, there were persistent gale systems sweeping through the 'Joinville line' that extended east off the shelf from Joinville Island into the Weddell Gyre. Due to this, we decided to head south to begin the Iceberg process study.

Prior to conducting the iceberg study we occupied a southerly ice station on 1st of February at approximately 64.6S where there was recently retreated sea ice. This allowed us to conduct a full two depth sampling effort. On the 2nd of February, we encountered a large ~1km long iceberg in open water and in around 700-1000m of water depth. It was decided to designate this our process study iceberg and we began immediately that evening with a 'fast cast' station within 30-40m of the iceberg on the leeward side. Over the next four days we stayed with the iceberg and conducted 9 fast cast stations and one hydrocast survey (9 locations within one 'station') around the iceberg that was accompanied by 16 sites of oxygen isotope sampling. The iceberg study concluded on the 6th of February and during the study the iceberg itself travelled 32 miles – predominantly north east with the current, but also to the east / southeast with the winds. The iceberg study concluded on 6th of February.

The following days required navigations and also anchorages and sheltering from extreme winds of up to 75 kts, first in Paulet Island and then in the Bay of Esperanza before a weather window opened up to begin our work on the Joinville line.

We commenced the Joinville line on the 10th of February after an overnight navigation with the station farthest east in 3000m of water depth. We then completed 3 stations across the line with full sampling by the 13th of February. Conditions were difficult, only allowing 12 hours work per day and overnight navigations were arduous, but with strong collaboration across the vessel we were ultimately successful. The Joinville line was completed on 13th of February.

With the two main objectives completed, we augmented our programme with three additional efforts. First, we conducted two stations focussed on sampling the diatom *Odontella* in Antarctic Sound, including a reoccupation of Tara Oceans station 87. Second, we conducted an additional full station in the Bransfield Strait to sample one branch of the outflow waters from the Weddell Gyre. Finally, two single depth fast cast stations in Deception Island to sample the impact of fumeroles and subsurface volcanism.

After waiting out another gale in Deception Island, we began our transit to Punta Arenas across Drake Passage on the 18th of February. This was largely conducted under sail, with no engine. Underway sampling, including aerosols, was maintained during the transit. We arrived in the Magellan Straits on the early morning of February 23rd. Overall, we sampled 20 stations, conducted 38 rosette casts, 35 nets and 8 GTRs. In doing so, we extended the range of sampling in the Antarctic further south and east than Tara Oceans.

We were away at sea for 29 days in total (25th Jan to 23rd February). We spent 5 days waiting for the arrival of the replacement oceanographer and 7 for the transit across Drake to Punta Arenas. Further activity days were lost due to weather, but some of these could be salvaged for preparing ahead of stations. Overall, we arrived back in port early.

Figures 1 and 2 represent a graphic record of the science stations occupied.

Figure 1 Broad view of the cruise track, departing King George island (green circle), with science commencing in Antarctic sound and ending in Deception island. Red circles represent sampling stations and open symbols represent sampling undertaken by other efforts indicated in the inset box (e.g. circles are prior Tara Oceans stations). Shading represents bathymetry from Etopo5 and the black box denotes the iceberg study area.

Figure 2 Focussed view of the cruise track and sampling during the iceberg study. Shading represents bathymetry from Etopo5.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

A key difference for this leg was the weather, which meant that the 1.5 day Atlanteco ‘meso’ stations conducted on past legs were impossible. We could count on maximum 12 hours on station with conditions appropriate for the deployment of equipment. Even when the sea state was amenable, the weather conditions for working outside were challenging and needed to be closely monitored and managed to avoid negative consequences. Due to its fundamental role as a driver of microbial dynamics, iron was a key component of our study and so we had to integrate the Geotraces rosette (GTR) into our regular workplan. Due to the lack of regular use of the GTR in past legs, we were obliged to optimise its integration within the usual Tara operations. To begin with, we used the GTR at the end of the day, as had occurred in the past, but this left the operators out on

deck late at night sampling, often in very difficult weather conditions. To mitigate against this, we switched to deploying then GTR before lunch. Combining this with the deployment of most the nets before lunch meant that it was possible for the Operator D to take on some of the wet lab filtering. This was 'redeployment' of roles was crucial as it meant that operators B and C could share the GTR processing, while regular activities with the rosette continued. Operator F took on all BGC sampling and assisted with the processing of nets on board. In the end, we did deliver a means to sample 3 depths and deploy the GTR alongside the usual Tara Atlanteco programme.

The Iceberg study necessitated the ability to conduct many sampling efforts (either different locations or many depths) in one day. This would be impossible using the standard Atlanteco protocols. To accommodate this we developed a set of fast cast protocols. These focussed on omics and key BGC parameters and allowed enough water for two depths to be collected from a single CTD cast. Different days around the iceberg focussed on different areas: (i) radial sampling at two depths for different distances from the iceberg, (ii) multiple locations close to the iceberg only at the surface and (iii) across four depths at one location within 10s of metres of the iceberg (including nets and GTR).

Station ###	Date (Z=UTC) YYYYMMDDZ	Latitude	Longitude	A20 pump	CAST – Z02-D1	CAST – Z02-D2	CAST – Z04-D1	CAST – Z04-D2	Bow Pole	GTR	NET – WP11 20	NET – WP11 200	NET – Régent 680	NET – Régent 680	FAST CAST – Z0	FAST CAST – Z0-Z02	FAST CAST Z0-02-04	Hydrocast	BGC cast	hTSRB	Microtops
84	12/02/2022	-63.426667	-52.126	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X							
85	13/02/2022	-63.0642	-54.348417	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X							
86	14/02/2022	-63.426333	-56.642833								X	X						X			
87	14/02/2022	-63.398	-56.784833								X	X						X			
88	15/02/2022	-63.264817	-60.011333	X	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X							
89	16/02/2022	-62.9765833	-60.63375						X						X						
90	16/02/2022	-62.97009167	-60.683328						X						X						

FM20	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
3DEM20	50 mL falcon	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E20	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	0
S20	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23	0	0
PM20	Zip-lock	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MB20	4-mL-vial	0	0	0	0	0	0	16	0	0	0	0	0
CP50	Zip-lock	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F200	250-mL-bottle	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E200	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0
S200	5-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
S200-L	5-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0
PM200	Zip-lock	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MB200	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0
CP200	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F680	250-mL-bottle	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
F2000	250-mL-bottle	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E2000	250-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0
E680	250-mL-bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0
S680-L	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0
SP300	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0
MP300	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CP300	petrislide	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S025-L	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	0
S520-L	5-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	24	0	0	0
FM5	50-mL-falcon	0	0	0	37	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
E5	15-mL-falcon	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0
SEM5	petrislide	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AI	petrislide	80	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
AS	2-mL-cryoT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80	0
AF	Zip-lock	0	0	0	0	0	0	80	0	0	0	0	0
TOC	30mL bottle	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

TOTAL 1712 156 130 131 37 30 18 387 112 67 326 228 90

Appendix

Station plans:

Joinville line, 3 depth:

Start time	Duration (min)	Activity	Depth layer (m)	Protocol group	A	B	C	D	E
BREAKFAST									
06:00		AEROSOLS		Aerosols					x
		SETUP			x	x	x	x	x
120		Bow pole	0-5	Trace metals		x			
		VMP	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				
		A20 Pump (Z0)	1-3	Omics+		x	x		
		A20 Pump	1-3	HP, FC, HC, SEM				x	
		A20 Pump	1-3	Decknet					x
07:00		Vertical Net WP11-200	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
08:00	180	Rosette cast Z2 = 50m	0-100	Omics+	x	x	x		
		Rosette cast Z2 = 50m	0-100	HP, FC, HC, SEM; Decknet, BGC z0 z2	x			x	x
11:00		Vertical Net WP11-20	0-100	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
LUNCH (Manta)									
240-300		GTR z0, z1, z2, z4	0-350	BGC samples	x	x			
		Rosette cast Z4 = 350m	0-350	HP, FC, HC, SEM; Decknet, BGC z4	x			x	x
		Rosette cast Z4 = 350m	0-350	Omics+ (BGC z1, z3, z6)	x	x	x		
		Oblique Net Régent-680	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
		Oblique Net Régent-680	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
DINNER									

Joinville line 2 depth:

Start time	Duration (min)	Activity	Depth layer (m)	Protocol group	A	B	C	D	E
BREAKFAST									
07:00		AEROSOLS		Aerosols					x
		SETUP			x	x	x	x	x
120		Bow pole	0-5	Trace metals		x			
		VMP	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				
		A20 Pump (Z0)	1-3	Omics+		x	x		
		A20 Pump	1-3	HP, FC, HC, SEM				x	
		A20 Pump	1-3	Decknet					x
08:00		Vertical Net WP11-200	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
09:00	180	GTR z0, z2, z4	0-350	BGC samples	x	x	x		
11:00		Vertical Net WP11-20	0-100	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
LUNCH (Manta)									
		Rosette cast Z2 = 50m	0-100	Omics+	x	x	x		
		Rosette cast Z2 = 50m	0-100	HP, FC, HC, SEM; Decknet, BGC z0 z2	x			x	x
		Oblique Net Régent-680	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
		Oblique Net Régent-680	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200

Iceberg Fast Cast – 4 depth:

Start time	Duration (min)	Activity	Depth layer (m)	Protocol group	A	B	C	D	E
BREAKFAST									
06:00		AEROSOLS		Aerosols					x
		SETUP			x	x	x	x	x
		Bow pole	0-5	Optics		x	x		
06:30	180	<i>Rosette cast (z0, z2)</i>	0-100	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		<i>Vertical Net WP11-20</i>	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
	180	<i>Rosette cast (z4, z6)</i>	0-500	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		<i>Vertical Net WP11-200</i>	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
	240	<i>GTR z0, z2, z4, z6</i>	0-500	BGC samples		X			
	60	<i>Rosette cast (z6 for decknet)</i>	0-500	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		<i>Oblique Net Régent-680</i>	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
		<i>Oblique Net Régent-680</i>	0-200	BGC+Omics+Imaging	x			x	F200
		VMP (if time allows)	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				

Iceberg Fast cast 2 depth:

start time	Duration (min)	Activity	Depth layer (m)	Protocol group	A	B	C	D	E
BREAKFAST									
	STA 1	AEROSOLS		Aerosols					x
		Bow pole	0-200	Optics		x	x		
		<i>Rosette cast / A20</i>	0-200	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		<i>GTR z0, z2</i>	0-200	BGC samples		X			
		VMP	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				
NAVIGATION									
	STA 2	Bow pole	0-200	Optics		x	x		
		<i>Rosette cast / A20</i>	0-200	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		VMP	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				
NAVIGATION									
	STA 3	Bow pole	0-200	Optics		x	x		
		<i>Rosette cast / A20</i>	0-200	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		VMP	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				
NAVIGATION									
	STA 4	Bow pole	0-200	Optics		x	x		
		<i>Rosette cast / A20</i>	0-200	FAST CAST	(x)	x	x		
		VMP	0-200	Vertical Microscale	x				